

SELF-DEVELOPMENT COMPETENCE OF ELEMENTARY STUDENTS ON THE EXAMPLE OF MATHEMATICS

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Abstract: This article describes the specific aspects of the formation of self-development competencies in primary school students, feedback on shaping in the minds of students from primary school. In particular, the modeling of classes through computer technology in primary classes is aimed at increasing the knowledge of students, the formation of practical skills in them, and the opinion on the subject of mullahazas are presented.

Keywords: self-development, competence, computer, education, modern education, lesson, technology.

1 INTRODUCTION

President Of Our Country Sh.M.Mirziyoyev said that "our young people have independent thinking, high intellectual and spiritual potential and will be able to grow up to their peers on a global scale as people who do not empty themselves in any field, to be happy, mobilize all the strength and capabilities of our state and society, " calling for a qualitative and effective organization of education, especially, upbringing as a person with high intellectual and spiritual potential is one of the pressing issues of today. The concept of development of the public education system in our republic was approved until 2030, five initiatives were put into practice, which included comprehensive measures aimed at creating additional conditions for youth education, state educational standards and science curricula based on a competency approach to general secondary education were developed, normative foundations of participation in international studies for assessing the quality of education were created. Based on these grounds, today we are using computers and information technology to organize classes in all schools, that is, in elementary grades.

2 Manuscript Preparation

Competence in mathematical literacy, awareness of innovations in science and technology and use – implies the formation of skills to be able to draw up personal, family, professional and economic plans based on accurate calculations, to read various diagrams, drawings and models in everyday activities, to use science and technology innovations that relieve human labor, increase labor productivity, lead to favorable conditions. These competencies are formed in students through general education subjects.

General competencies related to science are also formed in students based on the content of each general education subject. Therefore, the science of mathematics develops a person's intellect, attention, cultivates perseverance and willpower to achieve the intended goal, provides algorithmic-style discipline and expands his thinking. Mathematics is the basis of knowledge of the universe, and tevarak-the disclosure of specific laws of surrounding events and phenomena, is important in the development of production, science-technology and technology.

In order to increase the efficiency of the educational system in our republic by introducing a competency approach in the educational system of Uzbekistan based on the European experience, selecting the educational competencies to be formed and integrating them into the educational system, this competency system was adopted. There are different definitions, approaches to the word competence. In particular, the "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" describes competence as: competence (lot. competeo – I am achieving, worthy, worthy) - a certain state body (local self-governing body) or a circle of powers, rights and duties of an official, established by law, charter or other document; it either means knowledge in this area, experience.

Taking into account the potential of previously formed scientific schools in our country, the development of the fields of Mathematics, Chemistry, Biology, geological science and development was selected this year, based on the directions of our national interests and development at the present stage. Computer - today is an important means of obtaining and processing information, the speed of which delights the imagination. Therefore, it is permissible to consider the introduction of these tools into the educational process as natural in the present period. For example, by organizing mathematics lessons in elementary classes based on computer technology, it allows you to effectively master the material mentioned, activating the activity of Mathematical Thinking. Allows you to model and show processes that are difficult to demonstrate in practice. In addition to the pace of study of the material corresponding to the topic mentioned in the lesson, its understanding, comprehension makes it possible to conduct training in a one-on-one (individual) form.

2.3 Second Section

Through the use of a computer in the classroom in order to form the skills of self-development competence of students in mathematics lessons, the teacher not only gives students a certain amount of training during his training, but also achieves the formation of a passion for finding other information in them from various means, independently. The better the movement of students to know independently, the more efficiently and qualitatively the training will pass. By using computer

techniques and organizing classes, it increases the chances of students doing independent work, while the teacher can control the process of mastering the material mentioned in various forms. Educational innovation can be said to consist of form, method and technology that can guarantee a much more effective result than before, applied in order to solve an existing problem in the educational sphere or educational process on the basis of a new approach.

Improving the effectiveness of Education faced by the educational system today, by providing knowledge at the level of World educational standards and introducing educational innovations, the mature creator in every way must radically change his pedagogical activity, in particular, the pedagogical team of educational institutions in solving such tasks as maturing a harmonious individual with his own independent opinion, brought up in the spirit of On the scale of our republic, great attention is paid to secondary schools, and work is being carried out to provide our schools with equipment in accordance with world standards. Gradually, all educational institutions are equipped with computer technologies and screens. Through this, the quality education of primary school teachers increases.

Students, on the other hand, in a modern way achieve an easy assimilation of their understanding of computer technology into the subject that is practically considered. Today, teachers of educational institutions at the junction of the continuing education system, including General secondary schools, are faced with new problems, namely the task of improving the quality of mastering the subject being taught. In this regard, different methods are also used in teaching mathematics, the main goal of which is to easily master the teaching of mathematics. Work with students is carried out in each lesson with several concepts. Each of these concepts can be mastered at different stages of this lesson.

When understanding each concept is carried out by repeating, remembering another concept in a lesson organized through computer technology, this concept serves to explain further concepts. In the teaching process, each teaching material is carried out with development, which becomes the foundation for understanding the materials that are taught after the teaching material itself. Looking at the process of assimilation of another concept, it is formed by the interrelated teaching of several lessons. Thus, the generation of mathematical concepts pays off not only in the lesson itself, but also in the use of modern technologists. We call such classes a system of classes together. Through computer technology, the lesson is checked by asking for a new topic in order to know the level of students' mastery of the topic after it has been taken. Then a brief recitation also contributes to the deepening of theoretical knowledge. For example, in the 2nd grade, children got acquainted with a new method of subtraction on the topic "subtraction in the form of $95 - 12$ and $86 - 14$ ". In order to strengthen, they

solve these examples at home: these examples are shown to students using a computer through visual materials. $65 - 280 - 5$ to consolidate the previously learned knowledge of the comparison of quantities, examples of such a view are performed. Through this, students will be able to understand the act of subtraction in an easy visual and modern way.

3 Conclusions

In conclusion, modeling mathematics in elementary grades through computer technology forms self-development competencies in students and is a great aid in improving the quality of Education. It is a very effective way to teach students mathematical actions, concepts. Because, judging by the current demand, social networks have developed, every student should be able to use the tools of technology appropriately. For this, first of all, the qualitative Organization of any lesson is the most pressing issue facing the teacher, ensuring the successful solution of the issue that they have just put, it is at this time that the activity of obtaining knowledge is accumulated. For this, the teacher is at the forefront.

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